

Sorbitol wash of plant tissues to remove secondary metabolites for DNA and RNA extraction

Category Experimental Procedures

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Version draft

Labels:

Step 1

This protocol was adapted from Inglis *et al.*, 2018 and from a sorbitol wash protocol under [protocols.io](#) under

DOI [dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.beuvjew6](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.beuvjew6)

Sorbitol wash: Scale protocol as required

D-Sorbitol 0.35 M, 31.88 g (MW 182.17)

PVP40, 5 g (For tissues that have more complex secondary metabolites, it is recommended to use PVP10, 1.7 g, PVP40, 1.7 g and PVP360, 1.7 g instead of just 5 g PVP40 - make separately)

Tris-HCl, pH 7.8, 1M, 50 ml (MW 157.60)

EDTA Dihydrate ($C_{10}H_{14}N_2Na_2O_8 \cdot 2H_2O$), pH 7.8, 0.5M, 5 ml (MW 372.24)

DEPC-treated ddH₂O to 500 ml, autoclave before using, store at 4 °C for up to 6 months, check for contamination before use.

Add 1% v/v B-Mercaptoethanol per volume Sorbitol wash directly before use.

How to use:

Add 1 ml of sorbitol wash per 100 mg of tissue, fully resuspend the tissue by vortexing at max rpm at room temperature until mixed thoroughly. Don't over vortex, this could cause the cells to shear. Do not exceed the ratio of sorbitol wash to mg of tissue, rather upscale to larger tubes as required. Centrifuge afterwards to pellet the tissue at 10 000 rpm at room temperature (this can be increased to a maximum of 12 000 rpm depending on how well your tissues pellet). Do not exceed 12 000 rpm, especially with multiple washes as this can lead to degradation of nucleic acids.

Remove the sorbitol wash supernatant (recommend slow pipetting not decanting) and continue with lysis based extraction method.

Recommendations: For DNA extractions, no DNA degradation was observed for up to 8 washes. For RNA, no more than two washes is recommended. For tissues with complex secondary metabolites, at least one wash is recommended with the multi-component PVP sorbitol wash and the rest of the washes with PVP40 only wash.

List of organisms on which the sorbitol wash has been successfully used:

RNA sent for RNA-seq and 3'mRNA Tag-seq

Eucalyptus grandis floral buds, xylem, phloem and leaves

E. grandis x *E. urophylla* hybrid floral buds, xylem, phloem and leaves

Pinus patula and *P. tecunumanii* needle and stem tissue

HMW DNA for ONT sequencing

P. patula x *P. tecunumanii* hybrid needles

Podocarpus henkelii

Podocarpus latifolius

Afrocarpus falcatus

Attachments

No file attachments

*This procedure was originally created by **Nadine Kleinhans***